

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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The phrase "Education is a matter of life or death for us, or happiness or disaster" said by the enlightened scientist Abdulla Avloni hundreds of years ago, has not lost its value even today. In fact, for us to be enriched with the world, the education of our youth, and in this case the process of educating them, is of great importance. Of course, from the first years of independence, great attention was paid to the reform of the education system in our country, and certain achievements have been made in this field. But in the era of globalization, it cannot be overlooked that science, technology and technology are rapidly developing in the world. This, in turn, places new demands on education and science. In particular, the most important issue of education policy is to maintain its fundamentality and to provide the individual, society and the state with modern quality education based on current and prospective requirements as a necessary condition for modernization of the state education system. At the same time, the scale of the reforms being carried out in our country today requires the active participation of professors, students, and all participants of the educational process in these positive changes. This, in turn, places certain serious demands on their level of knowledge and skills. Therefore, quality organization of the educational process, and for this, the issues of introducing new ICTs in classes and further improving the use of mobile programs are highlighted as an urgent issue of the current education system. Such devices are occupying all aspects of our life, for example, the education system is no exception. For example, mobile devices are widely used in mobile learning and distance education. There are such programs and functions available on mobile devices, with the help of which lessons can be organized even more qualitatively and effectively. The use of mobile programs in the educational process has the following possibilities: mobile devices are widely used in mobile learning and distance education. There are such programs and functions available on mobile devices, with the help of which lessons can be organized even more qualitatively and effectively. The use of mobile programs in the educational process has the following possibilities: mobile devices are widely used in mobile learning and distance education. There are such programs and functions available on mobile devices, with the help of which lessons can be organized even more qualitatively and effectively. The use of mobile programs in the educational process has the following possibilities:

1. Interactive education. Currently, libraries are no longer the only places where young people read books. Now, students prefer reading e-books and using educational mobile applications as a convenient method in the process of reading and learning. There are thousands of educational mobile applications available today. With their help, it is possible to change lessons that seem boring to students and make them interesting in an interactive way.

2. Class hours. Unlike classes in educational institutions, mobile applications can be used anywhere, anytime. Learning with the help of mobile applications is learning that does not depend on time. There are hundreds of students who do not understand and are afraid to ask questions during class. And with mobile apps, students can solve their questions whenever they want and review the lesson for understanding.

3. Electronic learning materials. Now there is no need to buy books and study materials as many books and necessary information can be found online. E-textbooks and online materials make the process of searching for the necessary information a little easier. It is possible to get the desired literature instantly by clicking on a single search button.

4. Ability to track achievements. Educational programs allow users to track the levels they have earned. Mobile apps are also useful for parents as they can directly monitor their children's learning process.

5. Efficiency. Mobile applications allow the user to study and solve tasks faster and easier. American researchers studied 2,300 students who studied online for three years. It was found that they remember only 5% of the information in regular classes, and three times more with the help of educational mobile applications and websites.

Despite the advantages mentioned above, the implementation of mobile applications in the educational process is still somewhat delayed, due to the presence of problems and shortcomings that await their solution on this path. Among these problems and shortcomings, the following can be mentioned:

- Insufficient electronic literature needed for the lesson;
- The negative impact of mobile devices and digital technologies on the health of learners;
- Incomplete provision of technical support of educational institutions for the application of technologies;
- The fact that not all teachers have the capacity to teach ICT in the necessary lessons, using the necessary methods, that is, they prefer traditional education over interactive education;

- In some pupils and students, the enviable culture for such education is not formed.

Despite the fact that there are several problems in the application of mobile tools to the educational process, the current demand is the transition to the digital economy. Nowadays, many countries of the world have already moved to the digital economy.

In conclusion, it can be said that mobile devices are also a form of digital technology. If all the evidences are considered, it is not difficult to realize that the role of modern technologies, especially mobile applications available on mobile devices, is incomparable in organizing the educational process, enriching the lesson processes, being able to interest students, and improving their knowledge. Of them, it is correct and appropriate in the educational process access is the key to success.

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